

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **711ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20 correct
0 mistake
0 Leak reaction
711ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:45
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:44
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 7, 2025, 20:29
90% accuracy	November 7, 2025, 19:59

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master Practitioners

Test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **511ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

20 correct	0 mistake
0 Leak reaction	511ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:24
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:23
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:22
95% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:21

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **779ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20 correct
0 mistake
0 Leak reaction
779ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:52
85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:51
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:24
95% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:23

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **769ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20 correct
0 mistake
0 Leak reaction
769ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:53
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:52
85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:51
100% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:24

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy 100%

Mean reaction time 1052ms

📄 Sharing my results

▶ Start testing

20 correct	0 mistake
0 Leak reaction	1052ms Mean reaction time

Historical records 🗑️ Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:54
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:53
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:52
85% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:51

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

📄 Suppression Master
master

Reaction speed test

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Select reaction

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Improve skills

test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **662ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

662ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:48
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:47
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 16:06
100% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:54

Data visualization

Performance Trend

Accuracy Analysis

reaction time

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

master

5482 / 3300 experience points

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

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Frequently Asked Questions

Improve skills

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **668ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

668ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:50
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:48
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:47
90% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 16:06

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **677ms**

[Sharing my results](#)

[Start testing](#)

20 correct

0 mistake

0 Leak reaction

677ms Mean reaction time

Historical records 🗑️ Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:51
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:50
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:48
100% accuracy	December 12, 2025, 12:47

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

[Suppression Master](#) master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **830ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20 correct |
 0 mistake
0 Leak reaction |
 830ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:53
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:53
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:51
100% accuracy	December 12, 2025, 12:50

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **760ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20 correct | 0 mistake
0 Leak reaction | 760ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:54
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:53
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:53
100% accuracy	December 12, 2025, 12:51

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **805ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20 correct
0 mistake
0 Leak reaction
805ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:55
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:54
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 12:53
95% accuracy	December 12, 2025, 12:53

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **558ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20 correct
0 mistake
0 Leak reaction
558ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 13:02
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 13:01
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 13:00
100% accuracy	December 12, 2025, 12:55

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **538ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20 correct
0 mistake
0 Leak reaction
538ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 13:03
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 13:02
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 12, 2025, 13:01
100% accuracy	December 12, 2025, 13:00

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **644ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

644ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:47
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:45
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:44
95% accuracy	November 7, 2025, 20:29

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master Practitioners

Reaction speed test

- front page
- Select reaction
- Inhibition response**
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It's been upgraded!
 ↑ You have reached Level 5.
 New title: Expert

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **775ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

20
correct

mistake

0

Leak reaction

775ms

Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:48
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:47
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:45
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:44

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

expert

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

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Improve skills

test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **570ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

570ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:53
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:52
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:48
100% accuracy	November 19, 2025, 14:47

Data visualization

Performance Trend

Accuracy Analysis

reaction time

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

expert

896 / 1000 experience points

Reaction speed test

- front page
- Select reaction
- Inhibition response**
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It's been upgraded!
 ↑ You have reached Level 6.
 New title: Master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy **95%**

Mean reaction time **632ms**

- Sharing my results
- Start testing

19
correct

0
Leak reaction

632ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:58
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:56
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:53
90% accuracy	November 19, 2025, 14:52

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

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Improve skills

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **637ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

637ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:59
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:58
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 14:56
100% accuracy	November 19, 2025, 14:53

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

master

测试模式: 干扰抑制模式

干扰抑制模式: 根据中间箭头的方向点击相应的左箭头或右箭头按钮, 忽略周围的干扰箭头

测试完成!
测试结果

准确率 **85%**

平均反应时间 **552ms**

分享我的结果

开始测试

测试结果

17
正确

3
错误

0
漏反应

552ms
平均反应时间

历史记录

清除

85% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 15:04
85% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 15:02
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 14:59
95% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 14:58

数据可视化

成就与挑战

抑制大师

大师

测试模式: 干扰抑制模式

干扰抑制模式: 根据中间箭头的方向点击相应的左箭头或右箭头按钮, 忽略周围的干扰箭头

测试完成!
测试结果

准确率 95%

平均反应时间 459ms

分享我的结果

开始测试

测试结果

19

正确

1

错误

0

漏反应

459ms

平均反应时间

历史记录

清除

95% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 15:05
85% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 15:04
85% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 15:02
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 14:59

数据可视化

表现趋势

准确率分析

反应时间

成就与挑战

抑制大师

大师

6

1289/1350 经验值

测试模式: 干扰抑制模式

干扰抑制模式: 根据中间箭头的方向点击相应的左箭头或右箭头按钮, 忽略周围的干扰箭头

测试完成!
测试结果

准确率 90%

平均反应时间 468ms

分享我的结果

开始测试

测试结果

18

正确

2

错误

0

漏反应

468ms

平均反应时间

历史记录

清除

90% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 15:07
95% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 15:05
85% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 15:04
85% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年11月19日 15:02

数据可视化

表现趋势

准确率分析

反应时间

成就与挑战

抑制大师

精英

1353/1750 经验值

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

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Improve skills

test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **473ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

473ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:51
85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:50
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 19, 2025, 15:07
95% accuracy	November 19, 2025, 15:05

Data visualization

Performance Trend

Accuracy Analysis

reaction time

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

Elite

1484 / 1750 experience points

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **501ms**

[Sharing my results](#)
[Start testing](#)

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

501ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

🗑️ Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:52
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:51
85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:50
90% accuracy	November 19, 2025, 15:07

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

[Suppression Master](#)

Elite

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **95%**
Mean reaction time **456ms**

[Sharing my results](#)
[Start testing](#)

19 correct
1 mistake
0 Leak reaction
456ms Mean reaction time

Historical records [🗑️ Clear](#)

95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:55
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:52
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:51
85% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 14:50

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

[Suppression Master](#) Elite

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

Inhibition response

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Frequently Asked Questions

Improve skills

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **656ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

656ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:58
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:55
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:52
100% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 14:51

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

Elite

⚡ Reaction speed test

- front page
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↑ It's been upgraded!
 You have reached level 8.
 New title: Champion

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **95%**

Mean reaction time **537ms**

- Sharing my results
- Start testing

19 correct

0 Leak reaction

537ms Mean reaction time

mistake

Historical records Clear

95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:59
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:58
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:55
100% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 14:52

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master champion

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **574ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20 correct
0 mistake
0 Leak reaction
574ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:00
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:59
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 14:58
95% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 14:55

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master champion

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **95%**
Mean reaction time **622ms**

[Sharing my results](#)
[Start testing](#)

19 correct
1 mistake
0 Leak reaction
622ms Mean reaction time

Historical records [Clear](#)

95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:03
85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:02
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:00
95% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 14:59

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

[Suppression Master](#) **champion**

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **90%**
Mean reaction time **550ms**

[Sharing my results](#)
[Start testing](#)

18 correct |
 2 mistake
0 Leak reaction |
 550ms Mean reaction time

Historical records [Clear](#)

90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:04
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:03
85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:02
100% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 15:00

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

[Suppression Master](#) champion

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

Inhibition response

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Improve skills

test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **95%**

Mean reaction time **558ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

19
correct

1
mistake

0
Leak reaction

558ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:05
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:04
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:03
85% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 15:02

Data visualization

Performance Trend

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Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

champion

2087 / 2200 experience points

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

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Frequently Asked Questions

It's been upgraded!
 ↑ You have reached level 9.
 New title: Legend

test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **95%**

Mean reaction time **515ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

19
correct

1
mistake

0
Leak reaction

515ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:09
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:08
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:05
90% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 15:04

Data visualization

Performance Trend

Accuracy Analysis

reaction time

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

legend

2221 / 2700 experience points

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

Inhibition response

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Improve skills

test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **518ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

518ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:10
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:09
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:08
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:05

Data visualization

Performance Trend

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Suppression Master

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2291 / 2700 experience points

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front page

Select reaction

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Improve skills

test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **650ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

650ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:11
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:10
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:09
95% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 15:08

Data visualization

Performance Trend

Accuracy Analysis

reaction time

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

legend

2361 / 2700 experience points

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **75%**
Mean reaction time **538ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

15 correct
5 mistake
0 Leak reaction
538ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

75% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 29, 2025, 20:55
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:11
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:10
95% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 15:09

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master legend

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **90%**

Mean reaction time **435ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

18
correct

2
mistake

0
Leak reaction

435ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 29, 2025, 20:57
75% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 29, 2025, 20:55
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 21, 2025, 15:11
100% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 15:10

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

legend

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy **90%**

Mean reaction time **471ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

18
correct

2
mistake

0
Leak reaction

471ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 29, 2025, 20:58
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 29, 2025, 20:57
75% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 29, 2025, 20:55
100% accuracy	November 21, 2025, 15:11

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

legend

Test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **627ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

627ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 5, 2025, 10:44 AM
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 5, 2025, 10:43 AM
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	November 29, 2025, 20:58
90% accuracy	November 29, 2025, 20:57

Detour visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Reaction speed test

- front page
- Select reaction
- Inhibition response**
- about
- Scientific background
- Application scenarios
- Frequent Questions

It's been upgraded!
 ↑ You have reached level 10.
 New title: Extraordinary

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **559ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

20
correct

mistake

0

Leak reaction

559ms

Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	10:45 AM, December 5, 2025
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 5, 2025, 10:44 AM
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 5, 2025, 10:43 AM
90% accuracy	November 29, 2025, 20:58

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

extraordinary

测试模式: 干扰抑制模式

干扰抑制模式: 根据中间箭头的方向点击相应的左箭头或右箭头按钮, 忽略周围的干扰箭头

测试完成!

测试结果

准确率 **100%**

平均反应时间 **688ms**

分享我的结果

开始测试

测试结果

20 正确

0 错误

0 漏反应

688ms 平均反应时间

历史记录 清除

100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:46
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:45
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:44
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:43

数据可视化

成就与挑战

抑制大师 超凡

测试模式: 干扰抑制模式

干扰抑制模式: 根据中间箭头的方向点击相应的左箭头或右箭头按钮, 忽略周围的干扰箭头

测试完成! 测试结果

准确率 **95%**

平均反应时间**486ms**

分享我的结果

开始测试

测试结果

19
正确

1
错误

0
漏反应

486ms
平均反应时间

历史记录

清除

95% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:49
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:48
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:46
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:45

数据可视化

成就与挑战

抑制大师

超凡

测试模式: 干扰抑制模式

干扰抑制模式: 根据中间箭头的方向点击相应的左箭头或右箭头按钮, 忽略周围的干扰箭头

测试完成!

测试结果

准确率 **95%**

平均反应时间 **487ms**

分享我的结果

开始测试

测试结果

19 正确

1 错误

0 漏反应

487ms 平均反应时间

历史记录 清除

95% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:50
95% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:49
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:48
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:46

数据可视化

成就与挑战

抑制大师

超凡

测试模式: 干扰抑制模式

干扰抑制模式: 根据中间箭头的方向点击相应的左箭头或右箭头按钮, 忽略周围的干扰箭头

测试完成!

测试结果

准确率 **100%**

平均反应时间 **474ms**

分享我的结果

开始测试

测试结果

20 正确

0 错误

0 漏反应

474ms 平均反应时间

历史记录 清除

100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:51
95% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:50
95% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:49
100% 准确率 干扰抑制模式	2025年12月5日 10:48

数据可视化

成就与挑战

抑制大师 超凡

Reaction speed test

- front page
- Select reaction
- Inhibition response**
- about
- Scientific background
- Application scenarios
- Frequently Asked Questions
- Improve skills

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **599ms**

- Sharing my results
- Start testing

20 correct	0 mistake
0 Leak reaction	599ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:09
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:08
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 5, 2025, 10:51 AM
95% accuracy	December 5, 2025, 10:50 AM

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master extraordinary

Reaction speed test

- front page
- Select reaction
- Inhibition response**
- about
- Scientific background
- Application scenarios
- Frequent Questions

It's been upgraded!
 ↑ You have reached level 11.
 New title: Extraordinary

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **743ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

20
correct

0
Leak reaction

mistake

743ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:10
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:09
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:08
100% accuracy	December 5, 2025, 10:51 AM

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

master

Reaction speed test

- front page
- Select reaction
- Inhibition response**
- about
- Scientific background
- Application scenarios
- Frequently Asked Questions
- Improve skills

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **795ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

795ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:11
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:10
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:09
95% accuracy	December 8, 2025, 15:08

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

master

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

Inhibition response

about

Scientific background

Application scenarios

Frequently Asked Questions

Unlock achievements!

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **788ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

788ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:19
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:19
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:11
100% accuracy	December 8, 2025, 15:10

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

master

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

Inhibition response

about

Scientific background

Application scenarios

Frequently Asked Questions

Improve skills

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **688ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

20
correct

0
mistake

0
Leak reaction

688ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:21
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:19
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:19
100% accuracy	December 8, 2025, 15:11

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy 100% Mean reaction time 632ms

Sharing my results Start testing

20 correct 0 mistake 0 Leak reaction 632ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:22
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:21
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 8, 2025, 15:19
100% accuracy	December 8, 2025, 15:19

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

Inhibition response

about

Scientific background

Application scenarios

Freq
Ques

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**

Mean reaction time **581ms**

 Sharing my results

 Start testing

0

Leak reaction

Historical records

100% accuracy
Interference suppression mode

100% accuracy
Interference suppression mode

100% accuracy
Interference suppression mode

100% accuracy

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

Inhibition response

about

Scientific background

Application scenarios

Freq
Ques

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **95%**

Mean reaction time **560ms**

 Sharing my results

 Start testing

0

Leak reaction

Historical records

- 95% accuracy
Interference suppression mode
- 100% accuracy
Interference suppression mode
- 100% accuracy
Interference suppression mode
- 100% accuracy

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

Inhibition response

about

Scientific background

Application scenarios

Freq
Ques

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **90%**

Mean reaction time **530ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

0

Leak reaction

Historical records

90% accuracy
Interference suppression mode

95% accuracy
Interference suppression mode

100% accuracy
Interference suppression mode

100% accuracy

Reaction speed test

- front page
- Select reaction
- Inhibition response**
- about
- Scientific background
- Application scenarios
- Frequently Asked Questions
- Improve skills

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **85%**

Mean reaction time **536ms**

- Sharing my results
- Start testing

17 correct	3 mistake
0 Leak reaction	536ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 14:57
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 14:57
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 14:55
95% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 14:54

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **80%**
Mean reaction time **480ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

16 correct
4 mistake
0 Leak reaction
480ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

80% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 14:58
85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 14:57
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 14:57
90% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 14:55

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy **90%**

Mean reaction time **475ms**

[Sharing my results](#)

[Start testing](#)

18 correct

2 mistake

0 Leak reaction

475ms Mean reaction time

Historical records 🗑️ Clear

90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 14:59
80% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 14:58
85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 14:57
95% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 14:57

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

[Suppression Master](#) master

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

Inhibition response

about

Scientific background

Application scenarios

Frequently Asked Questions

Improve skills

test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **90%**

Mean reaction time **471ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

18
correct

2
mistake

0
Leak reaction

471ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:09
85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:09
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 14:59
80% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 14:58

Data visualization

Performance Trend

Accuracy Analysis

reaction time

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

master

4331 / 3300 experience points

Reaction speed test

front page

Select reaction

Inhibition response

about

Scientific background

Application scenarios

Frequently Asked Questions

Improve skills

test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **80%**

Mean reaction time **502ms**

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

16
correct

4
mistake

0
Leak reaction

502ms
Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

80% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:11
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:09
85% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:09
90% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 14:59

Data visualization

Performance Trend

Accuracy Analysis

reaction time

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master

master

4389 / 3300 experience points

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!

Test Results

accuracy 95%

Mean reaction time 585ms

🗨️ Sharing my results

▶ Start testing

19

correct

1

mistake

0

Leak reaction

585ms

Mean reaction time

Historical records 🗑️ Clear

95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:13
80% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:11
90% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:09
85% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:09

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

📄 Suppression Master
master

Reaction speed test

- front page
- Select reaction
- Inhibition response**
- about
- Scientific background
- Application scenarios
- Frequently Asked Questions
- Improve skills

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **830ms**

- Sharing my results
- Start testing

20 correct

0 mistake

0 Leak reaction

830ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:18
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:17
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:13
80% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:11

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **712ms**

[Sharing my results](#)
[Start testing](#)

20 correct
0 mistake
0 Leak reaction
712ms Mean reaction time

Historical records 🗑️ Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:19
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:18
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:17
95% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:13

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

[Suppression Master](#) master

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **100%**
Mean reaction time **813ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

20 correct
0 mistake
0 Leak reaction
813ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:20
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:19
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:18
95% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:17

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Test mode: Interference suppression mode

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete! Test Results

accuracy 100% Mean reaction time 467ms

Sharing my results

Start testing

Test Results

20 correct

0 mistake

0 Leak reaction

467ms Mean reaction time

Historical records

Clear

100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:22
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:21
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:20
100% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:19

Interference Suppression Mode: Click the corresponding left or right arrow button according to the direction of the middle arrow to ignore surrounding interference arrows.

Test complete!
Test Results

accuracy **95%**
Mean reaction time **619ms**

Sharing my results
Start testing

19 correct
1 mistake
0 Leak reaction
619ms Mean reaction time

Historical records Clear

95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:23
100% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:22
95% accuracy Interference suppression mode	December 11, 2025, 15:21
100% accuracy	December 11, 2025, 15:20

Data visualization

Achievements and Challenges

Suppression Master master

Science Research Experiment Survey

Thank you for your willingness to cooperate with students participating in the research project by completing the test and questionnaire. We guarantee that your information will only be used as part of the research data and will not be disclosed publicly.

How should we address you? (You may use a nick name, stage name, or number.) *

However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

alex

Your age *

10-14

15-18

19-20

20+

Your gender *

male

female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

- 1
- 2
- more than 3

In which grade did you get your first smartphone? *

- Under 6th grade
- 7-8th grade
- after 9th grade

In which grade did you create your first social media account? *

- under 6th grade
- 7-8th grade
- after 9th grade

On average, how many times per week do you post on social media platforms? *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4+

After posting on social media, how often do you usually check others' responses? *

- Constantly checking and waiting.
- Check every hour
- Check when I am available at night time
- Don't care

How many follower do you have on your social media platform? *

- less than 100
- 101-500
- 501-1000
- 1001-2000
- 2000+

How much time do you spend on your phone each day for entertainment (excluding study-^{*} related use)?

- Less than 1 hour
- 1-3 hours
- More than 3 hours

How much time do you spend communicating with your parents each day? ^{*}

- Less than 10 minutes
- 11-30 minutes
- More than 31 minutes

How many times per month do you engage in activities with your family members, such as ^{*} outdoor activities, visiting relatives or friends, or traveling?

- Unsure
- 1
- 2
- more than 3 times

Do you have a close friend with whom you can share everything? *

Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

How many regular extracurricular activities do you participate in? For example: sports, clubs, volunteering, etc. *

1

2

3

4

5 or more

None

Science Research Experiment Survey

Thank you for your willingness to cooperate with students participating in the research project by completing the test and questionnaire. We guarantee that your information will only be used as part of the research data and will not be disclosed publicly.

How should we address you? (You may use a nick name, stage name, or number.) *

However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

1

Your age *

10-14

15-18

19-20

20+

Your gender *

male

female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

- 1
- 2
- more than 3

In which grade did you get your first smartphone? *

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- after 9th grade

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- 2
- 3
- 4+

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- 2
- more than 3 times

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Online

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1

2

3

4

5 or more

None

Science Research Experiment Survey

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How should we address you? (You may use a nick name, stage name, or number.) *

However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

Sarah Yim

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

- 1
- 2
- more than 3

In which grade did you get your first smartphone? *

- Under 6th grade
- 7-8th grade
- after 9th grade

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- 7-8th grade
- after 9th grade

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- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4+

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- Check every hour
- Check when I am available at night time
- Don't care

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- 101-500
- 501-1000
- 1001-2000
- 2000+

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- Less than 1 hour
- 1-3 hours
- More than 3 hours

How much time do you spend communicating with your parents each day? ^{*}

- Less than 10 minutes
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- More than 31 minutes

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- Unsure
- 1
- 2
- more than 3 times

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No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

How many regular extracurricular activities do you participate in? For example: sports, clubs, volunteering, etc. *

1

2

3

4

5 or more

None

Science Research Experiment Survey

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How should we address you? (You may use a nick name, stage name, or number.) *

However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

Alina

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

- 1
- 2
- more than 3

In which grade did you get your first smartphone? *

- Under 6th grade
- 7-8th grade
- after 9th grade

In which grade did you create your first social media account? *

- under 6th grade
- 7-8th grade
- after 9th grade

On average, how many times per week do you post on social media platforms? *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4+

After posting on social media, how often do you usually check others' responses? *

- Constantly checking and waiting.
- Check every hour
- Check when I am available at night time
- Don't care

How many follower do you have on your social media platform? *

- less than 100
- 101-500
- 501-1000
- 1001-2000
- 2000+

How much time do you spend on your phone each day for entertainment (excluding study-^{*} related use)?

- Less than 1 hour
- 1-3 hours
- More than 3 hours

How much time do you spend communicating with your parents each day? ^{*}

- Less than 10 minutes
- 11-30 minutes
- More than 31 minutes

How many times per month do you engage in activities with your family members, such as ^{*} outdoor activities, visiting relatives or friends, or traveling?

- Unsure
- 1
- 2
- more than 3 times

Do you have a close friend with whom you can share everything? *

Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

How many regular extracurricular activities do you participate in? For example: sports, clubs, volunteering, etc. *

1

2

3

4

5 or more

None

Science Research Experiment Survey

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However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

Ethan Wu

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

- 1
- 2
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In which grade did you get your first smartphone? *

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- Unsure
- 1
- 2
- more than 3 times

Do you have a close friend with whom you can share everything? *

Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

How many regular extracurricular activities do you participate in? For example: sports, clubs, volunteering, etc. *

1

2

3

4

5 or more

None

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However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

Ivy.....

Your age *

10-14

15-18

19-20

20+

Your gender *

male

female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

- 1
- 2
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Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

How many regular extracurricular activities do you participate in? For example: sports, clubs, volunteering, etc. *

1

2

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However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

alex

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

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No

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In person

Online

Both in person and online

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1

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3

4

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Luyi Zhou

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- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

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Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

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1

2

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4

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1

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
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Your gender *

- male
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Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

How many regular extracurricular activities do you participate in? For example: sports, clubs, volunteering, etc. *

1

2

3

4

5 or more

None

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2221

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

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- 1
- 2
- more than 3 times

Do you have a close friend with whom you can share everything? *

Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

How many regular extracurricular activities do you participate in? For example: sports, clubs, volunteering, etc. *

1

2

3

4

5 or more

None

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How should we address you? (You may use a nick name, stage name, or number.) *

However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

Eva

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

- 1
- 2
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In which grade did you get your first smartphone? *

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- Unsure
- 1
- 2
- more than 3 times

Do you have a close friend with whom you can share everything? *

Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

How many regular extracurricular activities do you participate in? For example: sports, clubs, volunteering, etc. *

1

2

3

4

5 or more

None

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How should we address you? (You may use a nick name, stage name, or number.) *

However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

Jaden

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

- 1
- 2
- more than 3

In which grade did you get your first smartphone? *

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- Unsure
- 1
- 2
- more than 3 times

Do you have a close friend with whom you can share everything? *

Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

How many regular extracurricular activities do you participate in? For example: sports, clubs, volunteering, etc. *

1

2

3

4

5 or more

None

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How should we address you? (You may use a nick name, stage name, or number.) *

However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

619

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

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Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

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1

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How should we address you? (You may use a nick name, stage name, or number.) *

However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

Tiff

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

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No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

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1

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How should we address you? (You may use a nick name, stage name, or number.) *

However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

Zimo

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

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How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

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How should we address you? (You may use a nick name, stage name, or number.) *

However, please remember the name you use, as you will need to use the same one in the second part of the test.

Isaac

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

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- 2
- more than 3 times

Do you have a close friend with whom you can share everything? *

Yes

No

How do you connect or share your thoughts with your close friends? *

In person

Online

Both in person and online

Don't talk that much

How many regular extracurricular activities do you participate in? For example: sports, clubs, volunteering, etc. *

1

2

3

4

5 or more

None

Science Research Experiment Survey

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Mr. S

Your age *

- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

- male
- female

How many Social Media account do you have? Such as Wechat, Tiktalk, Instergram etc. *

- 1
- 2
- more than 3

In which grade did you get your first smartphone? *

- Under 6th grade
- 7-8th grade
- after 9th grade

In which grade did you create your first social media account? *

- under 6th grade
- 7-8th grade
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On average, how many times per week do you post on social media platforms? *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4+

After posting on social media, how often do you usually check others' responses? *

- Constantly checking and waiting.
- Check every hour
- Check when I am available at night time
- Don't care

How many follower do you have on your social media platform? *

- less than 100
- 101-500
- 501-1000
- 1001-2000
- 2000+

How much time do you spend on your phone each day for entertainment (excluding study-^{*} related use)?

- Less than 1 hour
- 1-3 hours
- More than 3 hours

How much time do you spend communicating with your parents each day? ^{*}

- Less than 10 minutes
- 11-30 minutes
- More than 31 minutes

How many times per month do you engage in activities with your family members, such as ^{*} outdoor activities, visiting relatives or friends, or traveling?

- Unsure
- 1
- 2
- more than 3 times

Do you have a close friend with whom you can share everything? *

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Online

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Rylie Pak

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- 10-14
- 15-18
- 19-20
- 20+

Your gender *

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- female

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chloe

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Eric

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1/15

0

Determine the direction of **the middle** arrow

Accuracy: Baseline vs. Expected Distraction

Time: Baseline vs. Combined Distraction

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